

Being Open about the Unopenable: a series of workshops about open research in qualitative research with socially marginalised people

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Executive summary

A series of online and in-person workshops were organised between March and July 2023, including six online sessions and one in-person workshop, to explore the complexities and challenges of doing open qualitative research with the following different underserved and/or historically marginalised communities:

- LGBTQIA+ populations
- refugee and immigrant communities
- people living with disabilities
- individuals facing mental health challenges
- survivors of domestic abuse and violence.

Sixteen speakers and facilitators from academia and external communities (e.g.: NGOs; experts with lived experience of marginalisation) were invited to present their considerations and practices regarding open research in their own field. The discussions were designed to merge what are traditionally regarded as separate voices – those of “the researcher” and “the researched” – by focusing on the co-production of knowledge. These sessions touch on different aspects of ethical open science practice in qualitative research with marginalised communities. They also shed light on the need for more discussions and policies, from journals and funders, tailored to qualitative research, regarding open research practice. This would enable researchers to make informed decisions when planning to conduct ethical open qualitative research, not only in data sharing (which often dominates current open research policy) but also expanding the concept of "openness" to research practices across the whole research process in a variety of research designs.

We note that, although we focused on specific populations, speakers’ reflections are relevant to different communities, as speakers emphasised the need to recognise participants’ ownership of data and collaborate with them in decision-making over data sharing practices.

The feedback from the attendees also revealed their perceptions of what is lacking and what is needed in current discussion of open science. Attendees presented, for example, the need for qualitative researchers to be included in open research discussions and debates, which they feel is currently dominated by quantitative researchers; the need for a better understanding of what is open research and how to conduct it; the potential conflict between open data sharing and ethics committee guidelines; the need for greater discussion of open research in PhD supervisions, and further support for both PhD students and supervisors considering open research; their lack of knowledge of any standardised procedures and checklist for qualitative open research, and their fear of sharing data and the apprehension regarding the repercussions of sharing.

Background and aims

With the emergence of the ‘reproducibility crisis’ in quantitative research, scholars have been calling for more transparency and data sharing, commonly called “open science” practices. However, more attention is needed to qualitative researchers’ perceptions and needs in such discussions. Qualitative methods as conceptualised here refer to a diverse suite of methods for collecting non-numeric data, that could take the form of words, images or audio-visual recordings (Madil & Gough, 2008). Qualitative methods play an important role in the production of more in-depth and contextual research in social and behavioural sciences (Grigoropoulou & Small, 2022) yet open science discussions can often focus on quantitative data sharing. Given the personal nature of qualitative data, confidentiality and anonymity are major ethical concerns (Lamb et al, 2024). Additionally, the plurality of epistemologies and data collection modes involved in qualitative research can challenge data sharing policies and practices, which are usually based in positivistic, quantitative research standards (Prosser et al, 2022). Guidelines and templates for open science in qualitative research have been produced (see Haven & Van Grootel, 2019 for a pre-registration template). However, some have argued that these models propose simplistic solutions, and therefore are insufficient (Huma & Joyce, 2022).

According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), the goal of open research is to make scientific knowledge accessible and reusable for all – increasing transparency and trust in scientific information (UNESCO, 2021). UNESCO proposes that data should be ‘made available in a timely and user-friendly, human- and machine-readable and actionable format, in accordance with principles of good data governance and stewardship, notably the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, supported by regular curation and maintenance’ (UNESCO, 2021, p. 8). However, UNESCO recognise that open science is evolving, and these changes also necessitate transformation of the research culture. For this paper, we will utilise more the concept of ‘open research’ rather than “open science”, to recognise the complexity of the topic for qualitative research.

Our purpose for this project was to understand how to conduct open research in qualitative research. Our initial idea was to focus on open data or data sharing, as UK funding bodies have been promoting it as a normative practice, which presents challenges for qualitative researchers (Mauthner, 2016). Unlike open data, which assumes full public accessibility, data sharing involves making data available with the possibility of applying necessary restrictions. We envisioned that discussions on open qualitative research would center on implementing ethical and secure practices. However, as the reader will see throughout the paper, and as a surprise for us, discussions went beyond open data or data sharing. Speakers discussed several different issues related to ethical practice and co-production at all steps of the research process with participants, especially underrepresented populations, stating that they can be more at risk of suffering harm from research practices, including the risks associated with being identified. In qualitative research, as Mauthner (2016) argued, people share stories with the researcher, establishing relationships. Although speakers in our sessions had vast experience working with the populations in focus, they did not always have experience with open research and data sharing practices, and therefore discussions were broad and included their reflections and theoretical considerations about the topic and about ethical research in general. Moreover, some of those speakers, despite being academics, are themselves members of the marginalised communities involved in this project. Hence, they shared their expectations, preferences and concerns based on their lived experience. Additionally, although our project focused on specific populations, we came to understand that a lot of the reflections that speakers brought to light are important for any qualitative researcher, especially those using interpretive, context-based research methods and those working with participants that can be considered ‘vulnerable’ in different ways.

Considering the complexity of the topic, as well as our own research interests (i.e., decolonisation and queer studies), we believe that discussing open research with qualitative researchers is vital. Therefore, we proposed a workshop with 6 panel sessions – online, with a duration of 1.5 hours each - focusing on open science practices in qualitative research with so called "vulnerable" participants. In this paper, we have chosen to mostly use the term 'marginalised' instead of 'vulnerable.' During discussions in our workshops, the concept of vulnerability was frequently questioned, leading us to adopt this alternative term for the purposes of this paper.

We also conducted a final in-person workshop at the University of Bristol to explore different disciplinary perspectives and provide an opportunity for qualitative researchers in the institution to reflect on this issue for their own work. Our objective was to support qualitative researchers – including ourselves – in making more informed decisions and establishing best practices regarding ethical open research. Given the different backgrounds of the members of the organising committee, the event was interdisciplinary and cross-department between the School of Psychological Science and School of Sociology, Politics and International Studies at the University of Bristol. Invited speakers were from areas of psychology, sociology, politics, international relations, transport studies, management, medical sciences, and people with lived experiences/from nonprofit organisations.

By collaborating with social organisations and academics with lived experiences, we aimed to take community engagement seriously, where we recognise that any academic activity can be enhanced if produced with communities' involvement and experiential knowledge. We purposefully selected speakers who represented the communities being discussed. Interestingly, the importance of co-producing knowledge with communities and experts with lived experience was one of the most discussed topics throughout our workshops. A co-production or community engaged research approach emphasises collaboration with community members from the start of a research project, giving them the status of collaborators rather than mere participants (Tembo et al, 2021). Therefore, qualitative data is not simply collected by the researcher but created collaboratively with participants. Co-production recognises and values this shared production and ownership.

In general, our project aimed to 1) encourage transparency, openness and democratisation of the research process in all stages of qualitative research; 2) promote interdisciplinary discussions and knowledge exchange; 3) promote ethical awareness and discussions about open research in qualitative research with participants from marginalised backgrounds 4) centre the perspectives of scholars from underrepresented backgrounds and non-academics as our guest speakers; 5) specifically focus on what open research debates mean to people doing research with marginalised groups to promote diversity in research – and bringing those groups into the discussion. We intentionally focused on inviting speakers who identify as part of, or who work with, marginalised populations, as follows: LGBTQ+ populations, refugee and immigrant communities, people living with disabilities, individuals facing mental health challenges, and survivors of domestic abuse and violence. By doing so, we sought to discuss distinct and shared perspectives these groups held on managing sensitive data, locating oneself as a researcher while sharing an identity with the researched population and engaging with participatory and/or co-production approaches, amid the scientific push to data sharing. We aimed to have critical discussions to promote equitable research practices, ultimately advancing simultaneously open research and social justice. The objective of this paper is to present some of the discussions, considerations, key ideas and recommendations derived from the project. For readers interested in a deeper understanding, full recordings of the online sessions are available for viewing (<https://www.youtube.com/@Opentheunopenable>).

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Methodology

We invited qualitative researchers and people involved in social organisations and/or with lived experience for each panel. We aimed to create spaces of dialogue between academics and wider social communities and organisations. The sessions happened twice a month over three months (April – June 2023). We aimed to engage as many people as possible, and we had over 400 participants throughout the sessions, from across the UK and internationally, from Master’s students to established academics. Online sessions lasted 1.5h, with generally two presentations (one from each speaker), followed by a general Q&A session. For each session, we invited one speaker with academic expertise, and another with lived experience or expertise on working with people with lived experience in a non-academic context, such as from an NGO. However, these roles were often intertwined. Some academics were also experts with lived experience, and most experts with lived experience were also academics or have had experience with research previously. All sessions were recorded and are available on YouTube at <https://www.youtube.com/@Opentheunopenable>. Following the online panels, we invited postgraduate students and academics in Bristol to come to an in-person workshop about open science in qualitative research. We had 18 participants in the in-person workshop discussion. Details on dates and speakers are as follows:

<p>17th April 2023 Session 1 - Being Open about the Unopenable: Contextualising open research</p> <p>Speakers:</p> <p>Dr Amy M. Russell: Associate Professor, University of Leeds</p> <p>Zosia Beckles: Analyst of Library Research Support, University of Bristol</p>
<p>18th April 2023 Session 2 - Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with LGBTQ+ people</p> <p>Speakers:</p> <p>Dr Rosie Nelson: Senior Lecturer in Gender at the University of Bristol</p> <p>Dr Ibtisam Ahmed: Head of Policy and Research at the LGBT Foundation (speaker)</p>
<p>24th May 2023 Session 3 - Being Open about the Unopenable: People with disabilities</p> <p>Dr Elizabeth Mazur: Professor of Psychology at Penn State University Greater Allegheny</p> <p>Chris Cook: PhD researcher at the Institute for Transport Studies at the University of Leeds with lived-experience expertise</p>
<p>26th May 2023 Session 4 - Being Open about the Unopenable: Refugee/Immigrant communities</p>

<p>Speakers:</p> <p>Dr Marcia Vera-Espinoza: Reader at the Institute for Global Health and Development (IGHD) at Queen Margaret University</p> <p>Caio Serra: Immigration specialist who has a strong experience with immigrant communities and public policies</p>
<p>19th June 2023 Session 5 - Open the unopenable: Open research about mental distress</p> <p>Speakers:</p> <p>Dr Jacqui Lovell: Research Fellow at Warwick Medical School and Co-Director of the Survivor Researcher Network community interest company (SRN)</p> <p>Sonia Thompson: Co-Director of the Survivor Researcher Network and member of the Lived Experience Advisory Board at Kings College London</p>
<p>20th June 2023 Session 6 - Open the unopenable: Survivors of gendered violence</p> <p>Speakers:</p> <p>Dr Jane Ndungu: Post-doctoral research fellow at the Gender and Health Research Unit at South African Medical Research Council</p> <p>Dr Andy Gibbs: Social psychologist and senior lecturer at the University of Exeter, an Honorary Associate Professor at the Institute for Global Health at University College London and at the South African Medical Research Council</p> <p>Dr Rosa Targett: Research Associate at the University of Bristol, with lived experience expertise</p>
<p>17th July 2023 In person workshop - Open about the Unopenable: Interdisciplinary Explorations on Open Science</p> <p>Dr Annayah Prosser: Lecturer (Assistant Professor) in Marketing, Business and Society in the University of Bath's School of Management</p> <p>Dr Lucy Potter: Academic GP and is currently doing a PhD at the University of Bristol Centre for Academic Primary Care</p> <p>Dr Daniel Conway: Senior Lecturer at the University of Westminster</p> <p>Dr Robbie Clark: Lecturer at the University of Bristol in the School of Psychological Science (workshop facilitator)</p>

Analysis and Discussion

Overall, discussions went beyond discussing practical issues of “how to do data sharing” in qualitative research. Speakers emphasised how the concept of open research may encompass the entire research process beyond data sharing, from research design to dissemination and public engagement. Since we were discussing research with participants from marginalised backgrounds, some questions were posed: who has access to the data shared? Does it serve the communities where the data comes from? Attendees and speakers emphasised how the research process should be not only transparent for academic integrity and scrutiny but should also be transparent with the community being studied, involving them into the research process. Therefore, issues of consent, confidentiality, ethical concerns, and co-production were reflected upon. We will briefly delve into each session to specify key points and then provide a summary of the main themes generated through the workshops.

Session 1. Being Open about the Unopenable: Contextualising open research

In this session, the first speaker (third author) discussed how qualitative research is diverse and cannot be treated as “one thing” since it encompasses different methods and epistemologies. Therefore, there are different types of data, and concerns go beyond it being “identifiable” or not. Qualitative data is personal and contextual, and it is often a product of a trust relationship between the researcher and the participant. Therefore, rigid data sharing policies implemented by journals or funding bodies, for example, Nature and Scientific Data Policy; and UKRI (Prosser et al., 2023) lack the contextual nuance required for qualitative research, which often puts qualitative researchers at a disadvantage when trying to publish. The speaker presented Prosser et al (2022)’s (fourth author) arguments for journal policies tailored for sharing qualitative data, in which editors could assess papers depending on the quality of their argument for sharing data or not. Further possible solutions were presented including data repositories that are specific to qualitative data (e.g: Q-DaPS).

Additionally, the speaker reflected on ethical concerns related to sharing data of participants from marginalised backgrounds, who may not may not trust researchers, especially in health settings. Therefore, the speaker discussed issues of data sharing related to consent - do participants understand what data sharing is and the implications of it? VandeVusse et al. (2021) found evidence that this is often not the case; how can trust be established and maintained if the data will be shared and the researcher may not have control over future uses of the data? Is restricting access to the data a solution to keep the researchers’ and the participants’ control over what was shared? Some possible benefits were discussed among reflections: would researchers be amplifying voices of underrepresented participants if we shared data? Would the use of secondary data analysis alleviate participants’ burden on reliving trauma? Would data sharing be an opportunity to establish participants as co-producers and co-owners of data?

Finally, the speaker discussed the status of the qualitative researcher as often the collector and co-producer of data. Researchers with lived experience share their stories with their participants to foster greater depth of relationship. Therefore, qualitative data can be a process of collaboration which can also put the researcher in a position of ‘vulnerability’. Additionally, the speaker discussed tensions with the precarious nature of the job market in academia. She discussed how researchers who can access “hard to reach” groups are valuable but can often find themselves on short –term contracts, moving from project to project without the emotional labour of their data collection being acknowledged.

The second speaker (Zosia Beckles) continued the discussion focusing on the importance of adequate risk-assessment and pre-publication checks to ensure consent and coherence. She focused on explaining the University of Bristol's policies for qualitative shared data, and the support available for qualitative researchers in the institution, where research technicians and libraries provide tailored support for each case. They also mentioned the institution's data repository, where data is not necessarily "open for all" but restricted depending on necessity. They emphasised the importance of institutional support and early guidance for researchers, especially researchers dealing with sensitive data.

Session 2. Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with LGBTQ+ people

In this session, the speakers highlight three main aspects of doing research with people who identify as LGBTQ+. Firstly, the 'queer' ethical considerations involved in LGBTQ+ research. 'Queer' here refers to both the participants being queer, and the queer methodological consideration involved when doing such research. Secondly, the importance of openness and collaboration in practice, and finally, the significance of LGBTQ+ research being centred on community voices and lived experiences. The first speaker Dr Rosie Nelson began by defining some of the key concepts in the field, such as open research, vulnerability and queerness. Especially, they invited the audience to consider the implication of the idea of vulnerability and our relation to it. First, we, as researchers, often presume what and who is vulnerable. That ability puts the power or the onus of judgment on the researchers. Equally, seeing LGBTQ+ people as vulnerable or sensitive reaffirms the otherness and struggle they often face in society. Moreover, we need to think whether that framing appropriately understands the social relations to especially trans and non-binary people. In some cases, the ethical guidance based on research 'sensitivity' might not apply. For example, the traditional notion of anonymity, might not be applied or guaranteed in the same way for say, trans people who actively seeks visibility and sees participating in research as a form of activism.

They indicated that open research can be understood in three ways: open data, open publications, and open findings, with open data being the collection of raw data made available for other researchers to analyse. They emphasised that openness in research with LGBTQ+ communities is not just about sharing data, but also about critically engaging with the ethical and trustworthy conduct of research, considering the purpose of open research in relation to participants and the field of study, and addressing possible concerns, for example, about replicability, validity, credibility, or rigor based on specific research context. Hence, some concerns were raised on open LGBTQ+ data in relation to the definition above. First, though often anonymised, putting sensitive LGBTQ+ data in a public space could still lead to targeted violence and discrimination against individuals based on their sexual and gender identities, as it is easier to identify certain people when the data could be read unedited, such as an interview or a story shared by the participants. Second, the intellectual risk involved is that of different or even misleading interpretations due to researchers' positionality, such as someone who is trans positive versus someone who has a gender critical view. Moreover, different methods of gathering data in research, such as collecting personal stories or public narratives, could give the conversation involved very different focuses, which is not necessarily emphasised in secondary data. In turn, the variations in interpretation could have very different political implications. Moreover, LGBTQ+ researchers are often particularly situated, and based on mutual relationships and care, even more so than other qualitative researchers. Hence, reinterpretation of those data that is based on very specific inter-subjectivities, conversations and experiences is difficult. They point out that this does not mean that qualitative researchers cannot engage with open research practices as there are excellent examples out there. Rather, Nelson wants to emphasise the challenges of doing so with the particular kind of queer research that uses queer methodologies. For example, embodied visual journaling, zine making, art practice based methods, to name a few.

Nelson emphasised how academics need to consider ethical conduct and data protection when conducting open research with LGBTQ+ communities, and that the answers to these concerns are always contextually dependent.

Another question is if the queer data is ‘too queer’ for the database in the traditional sense as slippage and affect in queer experience are difficult to capture in traditional open data formats. For example, sometimes queer researchers’ interpretation of the interview data is not only based on the transcripts, but also the emotions expressed through body languages and facial expressions during the interview. A mutual process of queer coding and decoding might be involved. Moreover, queer researchers’ own identity and reflexivity also influence the understanding of certain queer-coded language and experiences. These things are hard to be captured and presented in the traditional format of ‘open data’.

Dr Ibtisam Ahmed, the second speaker of the session comes from an alternative perspective with his position of the Head of Policy and Research at LGBT Foundation. He discussed how, in open research with LGBTQ+ communities, it is crucial to prioritise inclusivity, listen to communities, and co-produce research with community consultation in research design to ensure ethical safeguarding of participants, as well as to create inclusive and impactful research. He emphasised how every LGBTQ+ person and community member have valuable knowledge through their lived experiences, which is essential for contextualising and humanising raw data in research. He encouraged community consultation and feedback as an essential stage of research design to ensure inclusivity and consideration of community needs. Moreover, Ibtisam pointed out that language and terminology in research with LGBTQ+ communities must be inclusive, also considering context and demographics. It is important to use language that aligns with community identification and preference. Hence, it is vital to consult with communities directly impacted to accurately represent LGBTQ+ communities in research (for example, including intersectional identities and race/ethnicity), as outdated and non-inclusive language in demographic monitoring questions can lead to errors.

In line with Dr Nelson, Ahmed also discussed the ethical concerns in LGBTQ+ research. He discussed how researchers need to be aware of their own positionality and consider the context and levels of ethical safeguarding needed for participants as co-researchers, while also recognising the agency and autonomy of participants and having open and honest conversations with community members before obtaining ethical consent for data sharing. Researchers also need to acknowledge their biases, have ongoing conversations about improving the research process, and integrate ethics beyond prescribed ethical guidelines, to meaningfully engage with and share perspectives with the LGBTQ+ community. Both original and secondary researchers should engage in clear and accurate methodological reporting and reflection when analysing existing datasets. Being transparent in how the researchers approach openly shared data could mitigate the risk of misleading interpretation and/or create opportunities of monitoring from within the community. However, what exactly is appropriate practice is still not well understood and needs to be further discussed and studied.

Session 3. Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with people with disabilities

In this session, the speakers Dr Elizabeth Mazur and Chris Cook discussed issues related to disability research, with less focus on open data or data sharing, but providing considerations for ethical practice. They advocated for the use of the social model of disability, rather than a medical model, emphasising how “disability” is only a concept because of non-inclusive social environments and beliefs about what is “normal”. They discussed how this “social model of disability” (Olkin & Pledger, 2003) approach is important to challenge stereotypes by shifting the perspective from the individual to the context and environment that disables people. Mazur pointed out that despite the significant impact of disability on people's lives, it is often

overlooked as an underrepresented background identity, particularly in the field of clinical psychology. Moreover, she discussed how disability is often seen as the defining characteristic of individuals, but people with disabilities may not view their disability as the most important part of their lives, and the medical model focuses on what a person cannot do rather than the joys they experience.

Furthermore, she discussed how the social model of disability challenges medically oriented research by promoting health and resilience, incorporating people with lived experience into the process, and examining the social, political, economic, and legal issues related with disability. When it comes to conducting the research, methods and sample selection in research with people with disabilities should be carefully considered, including the wording of questions, recruitment avenues, inclusion of other intersecting minority statuses, and the inclusion or exclusion of people with disabilities in the sample. She discussed how it is also important to include a diverse range of disabilities in research samples and suggested using a checklist to ask participants about their disability status, while also emphasising the need to evaluate research findings and consider their implications for policy and clinical practice.

Both speakers highlighted the importance of using appropriate language when referring to people with disabilities, including the difference between person first and identity first language, emphasising the need to respect individual preferences in how they are described. People with disabilities should not be referred to only as a collective group, as it is important to recognise and understand individual experiences and preferences, as well as the complexities of non-visible disabilities. They discussed how it is important not to make assumptions or require proof of disability. This discussion highlighted the role of metadata and its role in describing data and ensuring the correct representation of participants. Chris, as an early-career academic with lived experience of being blind (his preferred term), highlighted that a disabled researcher can provide unique insights in the research process. However, non-disabled researchers can also gather valuable data by maintaining ethical practices and building trust with participants.

Session 4. Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with refugee and immigrant communities

In this session, speakers emphasised the need for co-production, reflections about ethics and safety, as well as culturally appropriate practices. The first speaker (Dr Marcia Vera-Espinoza) expanded the concept of open research beyond just open data, encompassing the entire research process. She reflected on how open science discussions need to address how open and transparent research should not only be targeted to academics and funders, but also to participants and other members of the community being studied. Therefore, in the process of knowledge production, the experiences of the community itself should determine what open research practices are implemented or not – such as in co-production research. As such, she argued that open research is intrinsically linked to research ethics. Given that migrants and refugees face precarious visa situations, it is important to reflect beyond “prescriptive” ethics and consider a “case by case” approach, establishing trust with participants and prioritising their needs, which can be sometimes at odds with institutional ethics. In refugee research, for example, prioritising participants' safety and addressing their legal concerns can sometimes outweigh adherence to standard research and institutional requirements. Therefore, the same approach should be taken when deciding about open research practices: as an ethical issue that requires reflexivity.

She reflected particularly about the perceived “vulnerability” of refugee and migrant participants given their dependence on governance practices that determine their entry into a country, focusing on bordering practices and the impact on their lives, particularly in Latin America. Refugees and immigrants often advocate for their inclusion and representation,

actively working towards change. They may find themselves in vulnerable circumstances due to displacement and exclusion, but it is important to recognise that vulnerability is not inherent to their identity and that categories such as migrant and refugee are socially constructed and subject to change. It is imperative that researchers do not diminish the expertise and agency of refugee and immigrant communities, as the data produced is based on their lives. The speaker discussed her own experience conducting projects examining resettlement in Latin America and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on migrant and refugee populations. Migrant and refugee communities faced vulnerabilities during the pandemic, leading to the decision to not interview them directly, but instead include local and national government representatives, international and civil society organisations. The speaker reflected on how NGOs and governments control data regarding refugee populations and discussed the ethical dilemma of having access to personal files and contact details without the permission of the refugees themselves, which raised questions about who “owns” their data and issues of consent, concerns which are already discussed by experts in the area, and are related to data sharing practices.

The speaker also discussed about how immigrant and refugee populations can often suffer “research fatigue” of being often sought by researchers to tell their stories, and warned about the need for caution, to avoid re-traumatising participants. The research fatigue issue is particularly relevant for “open science” discussions, since secondary data could serve the purposes of avoiding re-traumatisation (see Campbell et al, 2019). However, ethical reflections are still necessary: is that data generated through an establishment of trust with a specific researcher with a specific positionality? Does the participant understand that that story might be shared and analysed by other researchers? How could this secondary analysis affect the data? How do researchers ensure that their data is not traceable and can be used effectively?

The second speaker, Caio Serra, has extensive experience with government and humanitarian organisation working with refugee communities. He presented his experience working at an immigration centre in Sao Paulo, Brazil. There, immigrants could have assistance from social workers, psychologists, lawyers, and immigration officers, that would support them in accessing their rights in the country. He discussed open research as a practice that could potentially enhance transparency, inclusivity and amplify marginalised voices, generating evidence for policy change. However, he reflected on the need for ensuring safety and dignity of all participants involved in this practice. He emphasised the issue of communication, considering cultural and linguistic barriers, when establishing trust with communities. He mentioned the potential use of “cultural brokers” as a solution, people from inside the communities that could work as consultants or co-producers of research – with proper acknowledgement and compensation. He discussed cultural brokers as crucial for facilitating equitable research with immigrant communities and that research fatigue could be avoided by co-producing research with them, since they know the communities’ perspectives, experiences, and needs. This discussion raised questions about the role of the ‘cultural broker’ in agreeing to the sharing of open data and their role in understanding and explaining open research to communities.

Dr Vera-Espinoza and Mr Serra also emphasised how research fatigue among refugee and immigrant communities is caused not only by constant questioning but also by the extractive nature of academic research, where participants often do not hear back from researchers. Therefore, they discussed how “open research” goes beyond sharing the data but opening the research process. The use of co-production and accessibility was constantly emphasised by them, reiterating how it would be important to translate reports into participants’ languages and holding feedback sessions, sharing findings in an accessible and culturally appropriate format. They also instructed researchers to have referral lists to address specific challenges and concerns of individuals (to not leave them unsupported in situations of emotional distress, for example) and safeguarding protocols.

Session 5. Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with people with mental distress

In this session, speakers Dr Jacqui Lovell and Sonia Thompson emphasised the need for community engagement, empowerment and lived experience in research with people with experiences of psycho-emotional “mental” distress. They presented their organisation “Survivor Research Network”, where they do “survivor research”, a research methodology that emphasises equality and empowerment for participants (service users; carers; patients), aiming to drive social change (Rooney, 2023). They provide consultancy for researchers on mental distress research, striving to provide space for discussion, inclusivity, diversity and to challenge the biomedical mental health system. Their work is grounded on the framework for patient and public involvement in research, focusing on purpose, presence, process, and impact to ensure meaningful and effective participation at all levels of a project. Survivor research aims to be experiential, user-controlled, and holistic, understanding people's lived experiences and the social, economic, and political aspects, in contrast to positivist research which aims for objectivity. Survivor research aims to empower individuals with lived experience to shape mental health research, addressing power differentials and promoting participants' involvement in the research process.

They also discussed power structures in universities and funders, and its impact on mental distress research, highlighting that institutions have inherent biases and inequalities. They discussed how ethics committees and funding organisations often make it difficult to conduct participatory research methodologies properly involving people in the research process, trying to protect marginalised communities but simultaneously not adhering to their concerns. For example, they emphasised how racialised communities experience a greater level of discrimination in the psychiatric system, and often their needs often neglected. They argued that funders should consider peoples' needs before imposing certain practices, such as data sharing, to not pressure people into taking decisions that might not be comfortable or suitable for them. Therefore, reforming academic and institutional power structures was posed as necessary to enable a truly collaborative research process that puts survivors and marginalised community's members as decision-makers.

More specifically to data sharing, the speakers discussed the importance of consent, dialogical processes and allyship with participants. They mentioned a study where they used methods such as body mapping and poetry to reflect on diverse experiences. Participants were asked to lie down and asked to map different aspects of their body according to their journey, vision, criticisms, responsibilities, and feelings. They reflected on how participants were given the opportunity to choose whether they wanted to be named in the research report, which many answered positively, showing that often, institutional ethics guidelines are not aligned with participants' own wishes. Therefore, they discussed how data sharing in research on mental distress needs to be a dialogical process to question and change the nature of historical and social situations. Results of the study emphasised the importance of connection, relationship and belonging, making the researcher reflect on their own lived experience and question the ownership over the research. Hence, they also pointed out the importance of considering the researcher's positionality, and the importance of the researcher reflecting about their own privilege, journey and experience with mental health during the research process.

Session 6. Being Open about the Unopenable: Research with survivors of gendered violence

In this session, the speakers Dr Jane Ndungu, Dr Andy Gibbs and Dr Rosa Targett emphasised the importance of gender violence research being participant centred and reflexive. They also discussed the interconnectedness of gender-based violence in

institutional, local and the personal instances. Dr Jane Ndungu and Dr Andy Gibbs discussed openness and collaboration in addressing violence against women, including involving participants or organisations in the design of prevention interventions and giving them access to qualitative data. However, they emphasised the need of sharing data while protecting confidentiality. Thus, they discussed how it is crucial to co-produce knowledge and create safe spaces for sharing stories. For example, sharing transcripts of interviews can be challenging due to the potential of identifying participants, and the speakers discussed the difficulty and complexity of how to address this issue.

They discussed how the risk of identifying research participants in studies on gendered violence can outweigh the benefits, especially considering the potential harm it can cause survivors and researchers who are also survivors. Therefore, in practice, research participants should have the authority to decide what information should be made open and to what extent, and researchers should respect their agency and involve them in the decision-making process, emphasising again the need for co-production. They highlighted the importance of critical analysis of data and creating receptive listening spaces, recognising multiple forms of knowledge, acknowledging power inequalities, and understanding that the process is not perfect, to co-create new knowledge and interventions. They also mentioned the possibility of sharing data within a specific group, but not necessarily with the public, highlighting the importance of reflecting on the level of openness necessary for research. Furthermore, they discussed that the interconnectedness and intersectionality of gender-based violence needs to be considered. For example, the importance of recognising and representing diverse experiences of violence, such as state-inflicted violence.

Being in the position of a researcher with lived experience, Dr Rosa Target discussed her work as a researcher, activist, and community organiser focusing on various issues of violence, including physical violence, state-inflicted violence, and microaggressions, and their harmful impacts on individuals and communities. She emphasised that gender-based violence is pervasive and survivors often experience multiple forms of violence simultaneously, highlighting the need for community spaces, ethical research, and intersectional understanding to support and empower survivors. As a researcher, she faced challenges in conducting ethical research on survivors of gender-based violence due to the convergence of interpersonal and state violence, resulting in the need to modify consent procedures and data storage methods to ensure her and participants' safety. She indicated that researchers conducting research on gender-based violence must prioritise the protection and anonymity of survivors, as survivors often have concerns about engaging with institutions due to negative experiences and the risk of perpetuating trauma, and researchers should be invested in eradicating trauma for survivors in their research process. It is crucial for those working with survivors of gendered violence to examine their motivations, understand the expertise of activists and practitioners, and be mindful of the complexities of terminology and representation to respect the participants' experiences and avoid limiting their identities. Furthermore, she also emphasised the importance of intersectionality, highlighting that gender-based violence and intimate partner violence should be conceptualised in an intersectional way, recognising that anyone can experience gender-based violence and that it can take various forms beyond traditional notions, such as violence against women and girls, and acknowledging the complexities of these experiences is crucial in representing survivors. Therefore, she emphasised the need for co-design with participants, engagement with community activist groups and the possibility of creative research methods and questions, as part of "open research" discussions.

Session 7. In-person workshop on Interdisciplinary Perspectives

In this session, held in-person at the University of Bristol and open to the public, attendees participated in three talks and one workshop. Dr Annayah Prosser (fourth author) first

discussed the complexities of conducting open qualitative research, particularly focusing on organisational and institutional challenges. She highlighted issues involved in open qualitative research such as consent, the "messiness" of data, and the potential legal risks for participants. Prosser emphasised that concerns around opening sensitive qualitative data are unique to each project, and current journal guidelines often fail to reflect these complexities. With data sharing becoming increasingly compulsory, she argued that the standards for quantitative research are being inappropriately applied to qualitative work. To address these challenges, she advocated for collective action among qualitative researchers and educators, such as pushing back against unsuitable journal requirements, using reflexive data availability statements, in which qualitative researchers can reflect on why and how data can or cannot be shared, considering interpersonal and contextual issues. She also encouraged the teaching of open science considering qualitative research and encouraging editors and reviewers to adopt an "open as possible, closed as necessary" approach. She stressed the importance of creating spaces for qualitative researchers to engage in open discussions, workshops, and training, and to ensure their inclusion in open science conversations.

Dr Lucy Potter's presentation focused on a project aimed at improving access to general practice for patients facing Severe and Multiple Disadvantage (SMD) in the UK. Dr Potter presented qualitative research co-produced with women with lived experience of SMD that involved collaborative efforts from GP staff and researchers. The project underscored the importance of building trust, trauma-informed care, and clinician empathy. Her talk highlighted the value of co-production, transparency, and inclusivity in research, aligning with recommendations for inclusive open research practices seen in previous sessions.

Dr Daniel Conway, the third speaker, shared his experiences conducting qualitative research on Pride events and LGBT+ activist groups in South Africa. He discussed challenges faced, such as assumptions about his identity as a white British-born gay man, which shaped participants' perceptions about him (Conway, 2022) and prompted questions about how the researcher's identity and subjectivity can influence the research process. Conway cited Burchiellaro's (2020) idea that researchers in LGBTQ+ studies may face a strategic opportunity for potential complicity in neoliberal diversity politics. He highlighted that activists' accounts can be both insightful and unreliable (Blee, 1993), prompting questions about researchers' roles when doing research with grassroots activists and elite institutions: partner, collaborator, or critical friend. Conway emphasised the importance of being an 'engaged and critical' friend (Chappell & Mackay, 2021). He noted the need to balance academic interests with meaningful change and consider the rights of participants over data. Although less directly on open research, his talk offered practical reflections on ethical and humanistic approaches when working with participants and managing relationships with them, which also aligned with ideas from previous sessions about making participants owners of the data.

In the final activity, Dr Robbie Clark presented the interactive workshop "Open Practices in Qualitative Research: What, Why, & When", and explored various open research practices relevant to qualitative research. The session covered key topics such as data sharing, pre-registration, and registered reports. Participants engaged in discussions on the benefits and challenges of these practices, particularly in relation to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for data sharing. The workshop highlighted the importance of considering the different categories of data (open, restricted, and controlled) when planning to share qualitative data. The interactive nature of the workshop encouraged participants to reflect on how these open practices could be integrated into their own qualitative research projects.

Key themes

The workshops provided a space for exploring how qualitative researchers reflect and experience open research, and their broad conceptualisation of what open research is. While there is a tendency to focus on sharing data, given that funding bodies and journal policies emphasise such issue, the discussions in our events expanded beyond data sharing to encompass the entire research process, including design, participant involvement, and dissemination. This expansion underscores several interlinking themes:

1. Opening the research process entirely

The common view of “open research” practices focuses on making research data publicly available. However, the discussions highlighted the issue of openness, not only in relation to the data but also the entire research process. Speaker also cautioned against the assumption that all data should necessarily be made open or shared, they emphasised the need to prioritise participants’ perspectives on if data should be shared, with who, and to what extent. Therefore, opening up the research process includes participants’ access to the data and transparent communication about research purposes, methodologies, outcomes and dissemination. It would also involve considering participants’ input in decision-making during the research process, as well as interpretations and conclusions. This practice could ensure that marginalised communities are not just participants but active collaborators with control over the research that involves them, making sure that the research and its outcomes will be beneficial for them.

2. The need for co-production: Participant’s agency and ownership of data

Speakers in all the sessions emphasised the necessity of co-production research methods in research with marginalised populations. Co-production involves working collaboratively with participants, ensuring that they have a say in how research is designed and conducted, and how findings are interpreted and used. This method goes beyond traditional research approaches, dismantling power dynamics between the “researcher” and the “researched”, challenging prescribed ethical considerations and advocating for a holistic ethical framework that respects participants’ agency and autonomy, particularly for those who may have experienced trauma. For research conducted with marginalised communities or individuals in sensitive situations, co-production is strongly recommended to ensure that the community's needs and cultural context are deeply embedded throughout the research process, making it fair and non-extractive (Spyrou, 2023). In terms of data sharing, co-production can empower research participants by granting them authority over the openness and accessibility of their own data, thereby safeguarding their interests and promoting ethical research practices, recognising participants' ownership of their personal stories and their right to decide how their data is used. This approach not only enhances the research process, making it more inclusive, but also aims to integrate diverse forms of knowledge, ensuring that research projects are aligned with the interests and needs of communities involved in research. It resists open research practices as a system of power exerted upon researchers and participants and returns autonomy to the people who create the data.

3. Challenging institutional barriers

Given these insights, there is a clear call for institutions, funding bodies and journal policies to adapt to these evolving dynamics of openness in qualitative research - they must prioritise inclusivity, transparency, and participant agency to ensure that research is genuinely fair and inclusive. This includes attention to and respect for participants’ perspectives when deciding what is “ethical” or allowed in the research process and in relation to open research. If making guidelines for participants’ protection, these guidelines should be made with consultation for

individuals from specific communities to have guidelines tailored for their own needs and be flexible in a 'case-by-case' approach, by, for example considering having people with lived experiences of members of communities as advisors in research projects or ethics committees.

In conclusion, the workshops underscored the need to broaden discussions of open research, emphasising equitable access, transparency, and participant control. By embracing these principles, a more inclusive and ethical research environment that truly benefits marginalised communities can be fostered.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our workshops provided some unexpected discussions that focused on different aspects of opening qualitative research. While we anticipated that data sharing would be the focus, speakers emphasised the need for transparency throughout the entire research process with the population involved, encompassing everything from research design to participant involvement and dissemination. It was emphasised that discussions of open research needed to be incorporated into research design and planning discussions with communities. This placed a strong emphasis in conducting inclusive, ethical and transparent research, particularly when working with marginalised communities, urging for their active involvement in discussions relating to the sharing of research data and findings. In every workshop, speakers highlighted the necessity of co-production with participants, while ensuring ethical practice, fostering trust, maintaining clear communication, and respecting participants' agency and autonomy. This approach goes beyond mere procedural ethical considerations, advocating for a more holistic ethical framework, especially when working with populations who may have experienced trauma.

With regards to opening or sharing data, a key proposition is that research participants should have authority over the openness of their own data, recognising their ownership of their stories and their right to make decisions in this regard. Participants should be able to understand and give informed consent to how their data will be utilised in future (if at all), with recent recommendations stressing participant consent for specific data sharing licences (Prosser et al, 2024). To do this, participants must understand shared/open data and its implications, generating a call to action for the research community to build open research into their co-production conversations. If we are to recognise participants as owners of their stories, it should not be our decision to share it, the decision must come from them. This not only facilitates the co-production process but also acknowledges and incorporates diverse forms of knowledge, fostering the co-creation of research projects that align with community interests. This seems a complex idea, but it has been implemented, for example, for Indigenous data in Australia. The National Indigenous Australians Agency, in 2024, has developed the "Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data", stating how Aboriginal communities should be involved in all stages of the data cycle, assuring their self-determination over data. Outcomes from the workshops suggest that a similar practice should be implemented when dealing with qualitative data involving marginalised participants. Speakers also emphasised the importance of correctly reporting participant demographics and contextualising data within metadata, throughout sessions.

Institutional, ethical and funding requirements were often framed as systems of power which can be used for extractive research practices. It is important that open research practices do not become a further system of power that disempowers participants. Considering these insights, it becomes apparent that institutions must embrace these evolving dynamics of openness in research, prioritising inclusivity, transparency, and participant agency. These efforts could be supported through more reflexive engagement and assistance from ethical

boards. As Mauthner (2016) pointed out, for data sharing in qualitative research, funding and regulatory bodies need to embrace flexible and collaborative practices, adopting a 'case-by-case' and 'context-specific' approaches. Only by utilising context specific assessments can open qualitative research with marginalised participants truly fulfil its intended purpose of being fair and inclusive.

Findings from the audience feedback

The feedback highlighted several areas lacking in current discussions and practices around open science in qualitative research with marginalised populations. The above picture shows some feedback selected from a total 68 responses. Key points from the discussion include understandings of open research, defining sensitive data, the ethical challenges of data sharing and open data, the low levels of information provided in education and PhD

supervision meetings, and the emphasis on quantitative research in open science discussions. Participants also discussed their perception of the absence of practical guidelines in open qualitative research, emphasising their own anxiety around data sharing and problems with the visibility of current guidelines. Participants highlighted positive outcomes of the workshops such as learning about co-production and openness, incorporating considerations and concerns from the communities, involving collaborators with lived experiences, and reflecting on their own ethical practices.

Recommendations

From insights we had from the workshops, we recommend the use of co-production methods or consultation with communities/lived experience experts regarding data sharing and open research practices from the start of any research process. Institutions and journal policies should be revised to address the specific needs of these populations, encouraging co-production and recognising participants' agency and ownership over their data. Participants must be involved in research design and must have authority to decide how their data will be used and to what extent it can or cannot be made open. Their voices must be prioritised over academic' guidelines, and therefore, data sharing must be decided on a case-by-case approach without rigid mandatory requirements, this includes promoting policies that recognise and support participant involvement and data ownership. This can only be made possible if there is increased public awareness of and trust in open research practices. Additionally, while we recognise open research guidance for qualitative research exists, in our workshops, there seemed to be a lack of awareness' about it both from speakers and attendees. There should be an increase in discussions, training, and education, to equip qualitative researchers with the skills and knowledge needed to implement these inclusive, ethical open research practices, especially for early career and post-graduate researchers. These recommendations aim to create a more collaborative and representative open research culture, that values and integrates the diverse experiences and perspectives of all researchers and participants.

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